

Workshop: Technology-supported emotion measurement

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Topic Emotion measurement is a vital aspect for new product development and product improvements (see e.g. Desmet & Schifferstein, 2012). New technological devices, data mining, and social media offer many opportunities to invigorate design research. The focus of this small workshop is the question, how new technologies can be utilized for design research and emotion measurement in particular. The range of applicable technologies spans from eye-tracking, to EEG measuring, to semi-automated facial expression recognition in photographs based on data mining technologies or crowdsourcing, etc. Furthermore, many traditional technologies for emotion tracking are becoming smaller and mobile, which allows also in-field research (e.g. EEG scanners). Triangulating different data sources might result in new insights and improve user research significantly. For example, measuring people's emotions in relation to their location (e.g. tracked through GPS or indoor positioning tools) might indicate the influence of the environment on that person's wellbeing. In this small workshop we want to present an overview of available technologies, outline our own experiences with several technology-supported research projects, demonstrate some selected tools, and develop ideas for new research approaches together with the workshop participants.

Purpose The goal of this small workshop is threefold: 1) We want to give the workshop participants an overview of technologies currently available on the market as well as upcoming trends. Some selected tools for measuring emotions will be provided for hands-on experimentation. 2) The workshop will be used to build a network of researchers interested in the topic. And 3) it provides a platform for jointly developing ideas for new research approaches based on new technologies. As a result, participants will gain new insights and ideas for their own research on users' emotions.

Keywords *Research methodologies and methods, New technologies, Emotion measurement, Science theory, User research*